

Ecosystem and Landuse Policy Group (ELPEG) Bulletin – October 2023

Introduction

Welcome to this, our third ELPEG bulletin of the 2022-2027 RESAS strategic research programme. The aim of this bulletin is to provide policy makers with updates on the research on biodiversity that is happening within the strategic research programme. The bulletin will cover work from Topic D4 (Biodiversity) and the biodiversity elements within the air pollution Topic (D1).

For this bulletin we have updated the one-page summaries of the seven projects within the biodiversity topic and the one project within the air pollution topic that covers the impacts of pollution on biodiversity.

In addition, we have [new section](#) provided by Jack Bloodworth, (Principal Science Adviser (Chemicals, Biodiversity), Rural & Environmental Science and Analytical Services) providing a policy update for the areas of policy relevant to ELPEG.

We welcome your feedback on this bulletin and if you have comments please do either provide them at the ELPEG meeting or contact Ruth.Mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

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Introduction to Theme D and how to find out more about the work on Soils, Water and Natural Capital

Theme D - Natural Resources is one of five themes in the Strategic Research Programme. The others are A Plant and Animal Health, B Sustainable Food System and Supply, C Human impacts on the Environment and E Rural Futures.

Within Theme D there are five Topics D1 Air Quality, D2 Water (inc Flooding), D3 Soils, D4 Biodiversity, D5 Natural Capital. ELPEG and ELSEG will largely focus on D4 Biodiversity and the biodiversity work in D1 Air Quality.

Each Topic has their own mechanisms for engagement with policy and with stakeholders:

D1 – Air pollution

The project on ammonia emissions is working specifically with the CAFS2 (Cleaner Air for Scotland Strategy) Agriculture and Environment Working Group (AEWG) and the project on particulates with the CAFS2 Domestic Emissions Working Group (DEWG). The project on air pollution and biodiversity is engaging with ELPEG and ELSEG. Contact Andrea.Britton@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D2 - Water (inc Flooding)

This Topic has established an engagement group with SG policy (teams working on Water and Environment, Flooding, Water Industry team, Drinking Water Quality) and a wider engagement group (including NatureScot, SEPA, Councils, Scottish Water, NHS, land managers and communities). A summary of the projects in this Topic was circulated with the October 22 ELPEG bulletin called "RESAS Strategic Research Programme Topic D2 water - Summary of projects (June 2022)". Work about one of the projects within this topic can be found at <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/achieving-multi-purpose-nature-based-solutions>. A new newsletter [Achieving Multit-Purpose Nature-based Solutions](#) has been launched (AiM NBS). AiM NBS aims: a) Develop a multi-scale empirical understanding of the impact of NBS based on hydrological, hydro-geomorphic, biogeochemical and ecological observations; b) Assess the water-related ecosystem services of a selection of NBS approaches on our landscapes and suggest ways in which the benefits can be enhanced; c) Assess the state of river corridors and their role in combating climate change, via ES impact indicator groups; d) Understand how to achieve transformative change via NBS that deliver multiple benefits and works across multiple sectors and scales (WP4). Contact Mark.Wilkinson@hutton.ac.uk for further details about work in any of the projects within the water topic.

D3 - Soils

The engagement will cover work in the Topic, Underpinning Capacity and other Topics in Theme D and with Themes A, B and C. It is envisaged that policy and public engagement will be delivered through the underpinning capacity (JHI-UNC-9) with other stakeholders engaged through the new 'Soils Network' developed in this topic. The Soils Network will include representatives of LEAF, Soil Association, Zero Waste Scotland, SAOS, NFU Scotland, AHDB. A copy of the latest newsletter produced by this Topic "The Soil Sentinel" is attached. Contact Eric.Paterson@hutton.ac.uk or Kenneth.Loades@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D5 - Natural Capital

A series of specific end user groups has been set up, one for each project in the topic. These involve, amongst others, SG, ONS, NatureScot, Defra, SEPA and the Office of the Chief Economic Advisor. A

summary of the projects within this Topic was circulated with the October 22 ELPEG bulletin called “2022-27 D5 Natural Capital 6 x projects”.

Please see the links below for details about the projects within the Natural Capital Topic:

- Bringing in Participatory Approaches to widen the scope of natural capital valuation (JHI-D5-1; Maria.Nijink@hutton.ac.uk): <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/bringing-participatory-approaches-widen-scope-natural-capital-valuation>
- Climate change impacts on Natural Capital (JHI-D5-2; Mike.Rivington@hutton.ac.uk) <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/climate-change-impacts-natural-capital>
- Galvanising Change via Natural Capital (JHI-D5-3; Kerry.Waylen@hutton.ac.uk) <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/galvanising-change-natural-capital>
The latest newsletter from this project is available [23_09_25_JHI-D5-3Newsletter_September2023\(final\).pdf \(hutton.ac.uk\)](#)
- Modelling the socio-economic, greenhouse gas and natural capital impacts of land use policy and opportunities (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk) <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/modelling-the-socio-economic-greenhouse-gas-and-natural-capital-impacts-of-land%20use-policy-and-opportunities-2>
- Synthesis of natural capital and valuation outcomes Alistair (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk) <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/synthesis-of-natural-capital-and-valuation-outcomes>
- Understanding the value of Scotland’s agricultural soil natural capital (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk) <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/understanding-the-value-of-scotland%E2%80%99s-agricultural-soil-natural-capital>

Contact Kerry.Waylen@hutton.ac.uk for further details about the Natural Capital Topic.

Nitrogen impacts in natural ecosystems

Lead PI: **Andrea Britton** (andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve understanding of the impacts of nitrogen deposition on Scottish natural ecosystems in the context of a changing climate, providing evidence on how natural ecosystems are changing, what is driving this change and how best to manage and protect them.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

- 1. Review of nitrogen and climate impacts on Scottish ecosystems** (Completed – see outputs)
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
- 2. Nitrogen and climate impacts on above and below ground biodiversity in alpine ecosystems**
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
Work has commenced to revisit long term vegetation plots 50 years after the first sampling to examine how nitrogen and climate change are affecting plant and soil biodiversity in alpine habitats. During summer 2023, 102 locations across Scotland were revisited. Vegetation composition was recorded and moss and soil samples collected for chemical analysis and DNA analysis of soil biodiversity.
- 3. Nitrogen and climate impacts on woodland ectomycorrhizal communities**
Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk
Using data from the National Biodiversity Network and new data collected from birch, oak and pine forests across Scotland, we are investigating how nitrogen deposition and climate affect woodland fungal communities. New fungal community data has been generated from soil samples collected under pine, oak and birch woodlands in 2022, with further samples being collected in September 2023. Data from 2022 already expand our geographic and taxonomic coverage. Many new taxa to the UK and Scotland are also being recorded, expanding our evidence base and natural capital.
- 4. Impacts of nitrogen climate interactions on ecosystem function**
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
Using long-term (20+ years) experimental plots in alpine heath we are investigating how warming and nitrogen additions affect carbon and nutrient stocks, nutrient cycling and above and belowground biodiversity. Sampling of vegetation and soils in the long-term plots was completed in the first year – data analysis is now ongoing to examine the effects of warming and nitrogen additions on the plant and soil carbon stocks and on soil biodiversity.
- 5. Modelling of nitrogen climate interactions**
Contact: mike.rivington@hutton.ac.uk
Starting in 2024, we will be using data gained from all studies to model risks to Scottish ecosystems from interactive impacts of nitrogen deposition and climate change.
- 6. Review of potential for mitigation of nitrogen impacts on Scottish ecosystems and metrics of success** (Completed – see outputs)
Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk
- 7. Experimental trial of nitrogen mitigation methods and indicators**
Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk
Starting 2023 we are examining the potential benefits of restoration in mitigating the impacts of nitrogen deposition on peatlands. Working with PeatlandACTION, paired restored and unrestored sites have been identified along a nitrogen deposition gradient. A range of biodiversity and biogeochemical metrics of nitrogen impact will be measured to determine ecosystem responses to restoration and their utility as indicators.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Nitrogen and climate: a review of the interactive effects of nitrogen deposition and climate change on Scottish semi-natural vegetation.](#)
- [Nitrogen mitigation: a review of nitrogen deposition impacts and mitigation potential in Scottish semi-natural ecosystems.](#)
- Further information and project updates are now available from: www.hutton.ac.uk/NINE

People and Nature

Lead PI: **Katherine (Kate) Irvine** (kate.irvine@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Identify and evaluate interventions, approaches and processes to facilitate the transformative change of how Scotland's biodiversity is framed, valued, managed and governed, and how to harness and more equitably distributed the associated benefits.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

For further information on any of the objectives below please contact Kate.Irvine@hutton.ac.uk

- 1. Nature and Economy:** Explore nature-economy relations and the implications of different framings for managing nature.

Fieldwork commenced, which includes interviews with stakeholders about perceptions of nature-economy relations. Preliminary analysis ongoing as interviews nearing completion.
- 2. Enabling inclusivity in biodiversity narratives:** Identify narrative and approaches which are usually outside of biodiversity research, and develop and evaluate audio-visual and interactive narrative tools and techniques to better enable their productive engagement for transformative change. Draft report.

Progressed co-design of audio-visual platform, including development of methodological approach for creation of - and inclusive user-engagement with – its content. Fieldwork preparation underway.
- 3. Enabling transformative biodiversity research and change:** Examine how novel management interventions and transformative research can enable more diverse, sustainable and just futures.

Identified a relevant peer-to-peer project through which to recruit clustered farmers. Revised research approach and commenced fieldwork.
- 4. Values:** To understand the different societal, economic and biological values associated with biodiversity within nature conservation and farming practices, and how these values may be leveraged and changed with transformative research.

Identified alternative methodological approach to assess biodiversity values transformation.
- 5. Harnessing Green / Blue Infrastructure for people and nature:** Focuses on how to assess green-blue infrastructure for multiple benefits through investigating the impact of different types of interventions.

Undertaking analysis of interviews about impact of participation in nature-engagement programmes. Refining indicators of quality of urban life for use in evaluating place-based interventions.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Project website: <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/people-and-nature>

Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers

Lead PI: **Robin Pakeman** (robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to identify how the "IPBES drivers", specifically climate change, land use change, pollution and invasive species, affect key parts of Scotland's biodiversity.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Global change impacts on sustainable upland land use

Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

We have started the analysis linking climate/weather to the dynamics of the plots. It appears that increasing winter rainfall has boosted biomass in the grass dominated communities, but that high solar radiation restrict productivity in the best grasslands. These changes in structure cascade through to influence the invertebrate, mammal and bird communities.

2. Collective landscape management of farmland biodiversity

Contact: graham.begg@hutton.ac.uk

A plan has been set up with a Farmer Cluster based in Aberdeenshire to support their adoption of appropriate biodiversity sensitive production practices. Monitoring strategies by scientists and citizen scientists have been agreed.

3. Using long-term aphid monitoring data to assess drivers of biodiversity change

Contact: ali.karley@hutton.ac.uk

Long-term aphid trap data has been collated alongside meteorological data from each trap location. Pesticide use data has been received from SASA and a request has been prepared for land use data. These datasets will be used to detect trends in aphid species abundance, composition and diversity in Scotland and the potential drivers.

4. Using Scotland's Caledonian forest as a model system to assess impacts of major climate drivers

Contact: alison.hester@hutton.ac.uk, jenni.sockan@hutton.ac.uk

Our "future drought scenarios" experiment on native Scots pine saplings already picked up differences in resilience from immediate post-drought measurements in year 1. We have now completed year 2 drought treatments and are continuing to monitor bud burst and growth of young pines in each treatment group.

5. Assessing potential effect of chemical pollution on the wild Scottish salmon

Contact: zulin.zhang@hutton.ac.uk

Having selected typical Endocrine Disrupting Compounds (EDCs) we are developing analytical methods for monitoring these chemicals in water and salmon samples. At the same time, we are designing a sampling protocol for collecting water and salmon samples from River Dee.

6. Improved technology to track invasive non-native pathogens and their effects on ecosystems

Contact: david.cooke@hutton.ac.uk

Amplification of the new marker is working and matched sets of samples with the existing marker are being prepared for sequencing for cross validation. Both markers will be tested on woodland samples from the Cowal peninsula.

7. Impact Assessment of Invasive Non-Native Species

Contact: michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk; ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk Eleven new cost estimates were added to the international database of invasive species costs, including three plant species whose costs had not previously been included for Scotland. The UK National Vegetation Classification has been linked to the Defra Plant health risk register and the pests most likely to establish in the UK that can be hosted on plants occurring in natural habitats extracted. Five methods to identify which habitats to prioritise for surveillance of plant pests have been compared.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Mitchell R.J. 2023 [The amplification of plant disease risk through ecological restoration](#), Ecological Restoration 31 e13937
- Cock P, Cooke D, Thorpe P, Pritchard L, (2023). THAPBI PICT-a fast, cautious, and accurate metabarcoding analysis pipeline. PeerJ, e15648
- Pakeman, R.J. (2023) [The Future of the British Uplands podcast](#).
- SEFARI casestudy Mitchell RJ 2023 [Which habitats are at greatest risk from plant pests and pathogens?](#)

Scotland's biodiversity: People, data and monitoring

Lead PI: **Jenni Stockan** (jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to help protect Scotland's share of global biodiversity by optimising people's skills, data, and technologies to ensure effective recording and monitoring techniques and data flows.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Creating a Scottish biodiversity inventory

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We have compiled data from the NBN and the last full inventory of Scottish biodiversity from 1997. There is a massive disparity (ca. 70K taxa) between current data on the NBN (ca. 22K) and the former estimates of ca. 90K. We are preparing a manuscript to highlight and explain some of the reasons for this difference, which is partly explained by improved estimates and changes in ecological theory on the biogeography of microscopic taxa. Comparisons are being drawn between NBN data and expert knowledge of particular groups (insects, fungi).

2. Improved reporting

Contact: kit.macleod@hutton.ac.uk robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

We have tested different methods of allocating species trends to habitats to derive habitat level trends. Weighting species by relative abundance across habitats and habitat area give more pessimistic estimates than treating species equally. We have also assisted with the writing of the State of Nature main report and the Scotland report.

3. Oceanic-alpine soil biodiversity

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

Building on our citizen science project exploring diversity of alpine soil fungi across the Cairngorms National Park, we are now working with volunteers to map all soil biodiversity across 270 of Scotland's Munros. The project was launched in June 2023 and >400 volunteers signed up in the first two weeks. We aim to collect soil samples from 215 new Munros in addition to the 55 summits for which we already hold samples. All the new Munros have been 'adopted' by volunteers who are now visiting them to collect soil and photographs for analysis. Sampling is taking place June-September in 2023 and 2024 and to date we have received samples from 111 new Munros, bringing the total sampled summits to 166. DNA analysis of this first set of samples will now take place over the winter period.

4. Monitoring approaches for outcomes focused interventions

Contact: cathy.hawes@hutton.ac.uk

An interactive dashboard has been created to visualise output from the Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term platform as part of the development of a toolkit for soil and biodiversity assessment of arable cropping systems. The dashboard will link soil, cropping and biodiversity data to allow growers to visualise how changes in crop management impact on system properties.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-highlands-islands-62150479>
- Partner in BIOSCAN project: improving DNA-based biomonitoring in the UK
- Article on indicators in *In Practice*, the membership publication of the Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management

Habitat management and restoration

Lead PI: **Andy Taylor** (Andy.Taylor@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To gain biodiversity in moorland and woodland habitats through evidence-based land management and restoration to maximise benefits to society.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1 How can public and private sector investors, at low risk, restore woodland habitats for the most multiple benefits to society in addition to increasing natural carbon capture and biodiversity, and what land is available for this?

Contact: matt.hare@hutton.ac.uk

This work package is focused on reviewing and developing the evidence base on the flow of benefits to society and communities (as well as risks related to climate change and investor behaviour) associated with restoring and expanding woodland habitats. We are doing this using an interdisciplinary approach that combines socio-economic data analysis, participatory community-based assessment and socio-biophysical modelling. In the coming six months, we will be delivering the results of our analysis in which we map the socio-economic benefits and risks that flow from 40 years of woodland expansion activities in Scotland. We will also be confirming with stakeholders the location of our two community case studies (one rural, one urban) which we shall implement in year 3 of the project in order to elicit local communities' perspectives on how many of these benefits and risks flow in their direction. Finally, we are in the process of creating a typology of different investors in woodland expansion and their potential behaviours. This typology will be used to add an investor behaviour component to our ongoing biophysical modelling, which will allow the analysis of future possible woodland expansion strategies across Scotland.

2 What is the impact of Muirburn on nature and how does this impact compare to mechanical removal of vegetation?

Contact: stuart.smith@hutton.ac.uk

Field experiments at Glensaugh and RSPB Abernethy have been monitored for the effects of muirburn management versus mechanical cutting on belowground soil biodiversity, nutrient cycling and microclimate. There is a lack of research on the impacts muirburn management belowground, particularly on soil biodiversity. Assessing soil nematodes, a key soil faunal taxonomic group, we found no significant impacts of muirburn on nematode abundance, community structure, species richness or functional group composition. Instead, temporal variation had a much stronger impact on the soil nematode community. Plant litterbags, nutrient probes and soil temperature loggers are being collected from the field currently and data will be analysed in the Autumn.

3 How do our ancient woodlands function and how successful is woodland restoration?

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We will assess a) change in ecosystem services and properties when conifer plantations are established on ancient woodland sites, and b) how successful restoration is in restoring these sites. Data on soil chemistry, taxonomic and functional biodiversity collected over the past year have highlighted strong divergence from the ancient woodland sites in the habitats investigated. The fungal biodiversity in particular shows little overlap among the six habitats. Fluxes of major plant nutrients and decomposition of labile organic carbon also show marked differences between habitats. The study emphasizes the importance of intensive studies which capture within site variability.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Project website <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/habitat-management-and-restoration>

Protected areas to tackle biodiversity loss now, and for the future

Lead PI: **Ruth Mitchell** (ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve our understanding of how to design effective protected area networks against a backdrop of rapid environmental change and how to measure the success of protected areas.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Can applying a seascape approach to marine protection benefit biodiversity protection and improve fishery sustainability?

Contact: neil.burns@sruc.ac.uk

Our work in 2023 continues to develop understanding of the mosaic of habitats required to properly protect marine fish biodiversity. Specifically, we are building knowledge on which habitat combinations are important for survival and growth of juvenile fish, including cod, haddock and whiting. The data collected from Loch Eriboll and Little Loch Broom now amounts to over 700 Stereo Baited Remote Underwater Video (SBRUV) camera deployments and has been used to build seabed habitat maps (paper in review). The camera deployments collecting data on fish abundances are also informing understanding of elasmobranch ecology (paper in prep) and supplementing data for two PhD projects.

2. How can protected areas ensure that threatened genetic diversity is safeguarded?

Contact: jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk

For this work we are utilizing our Scot's Pine common garden experiment with pine trees grown from known mothers from 21 protected Caledonian forests in 3 replicated sites across different bioclimatic zones. Genotyping work is nearly complete which will allow us to identify genetic markers for the specific traits we have measured in the field.

3. Can we identify refugia for species which are unlikely to disperse quickly in the face of a changing climate?

Contact: c.ellis@rbge.ac.uk

Data loggers were placed into three woodland NNRs, measuring microclimatic differences between sites, and within sites with respect to topography and stand structure. Site differences accounted for c. 70-80% of microclimatic variability (at the scale of 100s km), but topography and stand structure accounted for 20-30% variability at scales of metres or centimetres. Ongoing analysis is aiming to put microclimatic variability in a predictive framework, to inform woodland management plans for future resilience.

4. How do we measure the success of our protected areas?

Contact: ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

We have collated data from two long-term vegetation data sets from 1970's-2000's to assess differences in vegetation change inside and outside protected areas, across a range of habitats within Scotland. In total there are 1775 plots and we have calculated changes in cover for a variety of species groups such as grasses, forbs and dwarf shrubs and changes in the number of species in these groups. Initial results show that the dynamics of vegetation change are similar within and outside protected areas.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: mother tree, cone and seed phenotypes, 2007.](#)
- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: field phenotypes, 2013-2020.](#)
- [Long-term multisite Scots pine trial, Scotland: nursery phenotypes, 2007-2011.](#)
- Website: <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/protected-areas-to-tackle-biodiversity-loss-now-and-for-the-future>

Assessing the impact of changing migratory patterns, population size and diversity of greylag geese on livestock and public health

Lead PI: **Eleanor Watson** (eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To investigate the microbial risks associated with rapidly expanded resident and migratory greylag goose populations on Orkney, and assess economic, conservation and social impacts.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Investigate transmission of *Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Campylobacter* and antimicrobial resistance between geese, calves and cattle and the wider environment

Contacts: clare.hamilton@moredun.ac.uk (*Cryptosporidium*), eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk (*Campylobacter*) and nuno.silva@moredun.ac.uk (antimicrobial resistance)

Goose faecal samples have been collected during the wintering season (November 2022) and goose, cattle and calf samples have been collected during pre-and post-turnout of calves to pasture (April 2023, June 2023). Samples have been processed to isolate *Campylobacter* and *Cryptosporidium* and archived for DNA extraction.

2. Development of molecular tools to genotype geese

Contact: keith.ballingall@moredun.ac.uk

Methods to extract goose DNA from faeces have been assessed and optimised using local faecal material and DNA of sufficient quality and quantity has successfully been extracted for molecular analysis. Methods to amplify loci of interest for goose genotyping have also been optimised. Icelandic greylag geese samples have been collected and shipped at two different timepoints.

3. Engage with stakeholder groups to inform project progression, assess impact of findings and highlight successful approaches for related studies

Contact: eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk and beth.wells@moredun.ac.uk

The project has been outlined to members of the Orkney Goose Management Group and summary documents containing results for each farm are being prepared.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Project PI contributed to the recent publication [NatureScot Scientific Advisory Committee Sub-Group on Avian Influenza Report on the H5N1 outbreak in wild birds 2020-2023](#)
- Project PI attended [Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza \(HPAI\) Workshop: Research for Recovery](#)
- Project PI chaired session at NatureScot HPAI [stakeholder event](#)
- SEFARI case study prepared for Microbe Safari: A new web resource for the public and learners

Seeking multiple benefits from natural carbon stores in the uplands

Lead PI: **Davy McCracken** (davy.mccracken@sruc.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Explore the relationship between carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to detect synergies and trade-offs and identify land management practices that optimise the benefits derived

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

Our work is focused on SRUC's Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms where we are focusing on carbon storage (in the soil, and vegetation), biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation.

1. **Ground-truth existing maps of carbon storage potential and flood mitigation using on the ground surveys and environmental sensors to monitor rainfall and water flow, and expand the spatial coverage of these maps to include all predominant habitats on the estate.**

All progressing on track.

2. **Supplement existing biodiversity datasets, through the collection of new biodiversity data to expand spatial coverage to cover all predominant habitats present on the farm, and implement innovative approaches to monitor biodiversity (e.g., acoustic sensors and camera traps)**

Audiomoth acoustic loggers and camera traps have been deployed on lowland and upland sites for the second year. Work is ongoing to develop a guidance document for the use of Audiomoth loggers for detecting bird occurrence, with the aim of helping users identify and remove false positives.

3. **Trial scorecards developed under NatureScot's project Piloting an Outcomes Based Approach (POBAS) in Scotland and the NatureScot Civtech Challenge Habitat Quality app to determine how effective proposed scorecards are as indicators of wider biodiversity**

Liaison with NatureScot ongoing, with one online and one in-person meeting held at the farms in summer 2023 to initiate further testing of their Habitat Quality App and discuss issues they have identified with upland mosaics.

4. **Quantify the relationships between metrics relating to carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to identify synergies and trade-offs between these key ecosystem services, and identify land management practices that optimise these multiple benefits**

To complete in Year 4

5. **Utilise data from Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms to create spatial models of carbon storage, biodiversity conservation potential and flood mitigation for part of the upper River Tay catchment, and collect additional data to ground-truth these at several sites, to test the scalability of findings generated during this study**

To complete in Year 5

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Input continuing to discussions on how best to include biodiversity conditions on future agricultural support direct payments through participation in the Academic Advisory Panel advising the ARIOB process and the Programme Advisory Group advising on Scotland's Biodiversity Strategy.](#)
- [McCracken, D. & Thomson, S. 2023. Key considerations when including biodiversity measures within environmental conditionality. Economic Advice & Related Services to Support Development of a New Rural Support Scheme for Scotland RESAS 005/21 - W12.](#)
- [Members of Scottish Parliament's Rural Affairs & Environment Committee visiting the farms in November 2023.](#)

ELPEG Policy Update

Biodiversity Policy

The 'Tackling the nature emergency: Consultation on Scotland's Strategic Framework for Biodiversity' was published on the 7th September 2023. The consultation outlines:

- The first 5 year delivery plan for the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy;
- Proposed policy frameworks for nature networks and 30x30;
- Proposals for how statutory targets will be selected and set in the natural environment and;
- Proposals to update the National Parks legislation

The consultation is open until the 14th December 2023, stakeholders are encouraged to respond. The consultation can be accessed [here](#).

The Biodiversity Programme Advisory Group (PAG) has been key to providing advice thus far on the development of the Biodiversity Strategy and associated draft delivery plan. Most recently the group has been advising on the development of statutory targets for the Natural Environment Bill.

Wildlife Management

The Wildlife Management and Muirburn (Scotland) Bill was introduced to Parliament earlier this year. The Bill aims to update the rules around how people can capture and kill certain wild birds and wild animals, and rules around the making of muirburn (the controlled burning of heather and other plants for land management purposes). More detail on the Bill can be found [here](#).

The Scottish Government laid two Scottish Statutory Instruments (SSI's) on 21st June to implement three Deer Working Group recommendations. One SSI will remove the close season for male deer and come into force on 21st October, so effectively there will be no male close season this year. The other SSI will reduce the minimum ammunition weight to 80gr from 100gr, thus making non-lead ammunition more accessible. It will also permit the use of night sights to shoot deer. We expect that will come into force in early November.

Agricultural Reform

The agricultural reform programme to support delivery of the Vision for Agriculture continues to develop through a co-production approach. This will see at least half of future payments being conditional on implementing measures to improve biodiversity and/or mitigate and adapt to climate change. The new payments framework will be split into four tiers: Basic, Enhanced, Elective and Complimentary. More detail can be found on the regularly updated route map to agricultural reform [here](#). The Agriculture and Rural Communities Bill was introduced into Parliament on 29 September. The Bill aims to provide Scotland with a future framework that will support farmers and crofters to meet more of our food needs sustainably and to farm and croft with nature and will assist in efforts to meet our climate change targets

Relevant Scottish Government funded work outside the SRP published recently

The following commissioned reports have been published that are relevant to ELPEG:

[Research into Approaches to Measuring Biodiversity in Scotland](#)

[Defining rewilding for Scotland's public sector: research findings](#)

[Phase 2 Main Report - Developing Habitat Scale DNA Monitoring in Support of Post 2020 Biodiversity Reporting Requirements](#)

[Key considerations when including biodiversity measures within environmental conditionality](#)